

Beyond Open Research: Developing a Proof-of-Concept to Embed Quality and Reliability

Barriers and incentives to reproducibility and transparency in research data management lifecycle

Deterrent	Research data management lifecycle	Enabler
<p>Lack of knowledge, understanding or experience (e.g. students)</p> <p>If the funder doesn't ask for something specifically, you might not think about doing it</p> <p>No follow up, lack of peer reviews of data management plan</p> <p>If your study involves vulnerable people, there are a lot of different requirements for consent + forms to fill in</p> <p>Lack of time (time pressure)</p> <p>People sometimes want to keep their data to themselves. Sharing isn't in their interests</p> <p>Different disciplines have different needs and approaches</p>	<p>Planning and project set up</p>	<p>Promote a culture of data sharing</p> <p>Setting up infrastructure to support and educate both staff and students</p> <p>Training and education to gain experiences</p> <p>Resource or data management champion (to relieve the pressure and correct lack of clarity)</p> <p>More follow up and support from funders</p> <p>Set up a standard directory structure for everyone to follow/use from the start</p>
<p>Lack of communication between IT departments and working researchers to understand their real needs and potential solutions</p> <p>No conventions for file naming, which can make finding data later very difficult. Need for a formalised convention and for good practices to be embedded from beginning</p> <p>Loss of data when colleagues move on to a different post or organisation</p>	<p>Data collection</p>	<p>Permanent lab manager</p> <p>Part of appraisal</p> <p>Procedures for personnel exit - handover data and protocols. Checklist</p>

Lack of accessibility to data: accessing each other's data	Data collection	File naming convention agreed to and followed by all data collectors and processors. Samples and data
Data processing and analysis not trialled during acquisition so 'quality data' not always collected without that feedback		Shared folder policy
Old IT equipment that means some files can only be accessed via specific PC. If that PC dies some data is not accessible anymore		Regular review of policies and procedures. Understand if they need to be changed
Data storage: limitation in the capacity		Unlimited storage - server and tape
Compromising the amount of data you can export due to space e.g. not exporting negative results		
Data processing and analysis		
Paper based record keeping culture to physically share (data processing and analysis)	Data processing and analysis	Quality assurance/peer review for all data: a new post is allocated to each research project
Amount of data large datasets - still trying to figure out how to analyse and process it doesn't feel is ready or accurate to share		Data stewards - faculty embedded, disciplinary or domain-specific RDM support
Methodology is not yet robust - lack confidence to share		Within the institute, collective effort to process and analyse data workshop or bioinformation facility to help
Data archiving and sharing		
Password protected data	Data archiving and sharing	Consequences for not archiving
Can't find it		Open data platforms
Data archiving and sharing: Resources "umbrella term" consistency		Education
Cost of data maintenance		Standardised RDM policy for all Imperial
Interpretability (e.g. code interpretation clear where data came from)		Data archiving and sharing; more transparency; policies more findable
Not wanting to share		Better data management plans
Corrupted data		Make PI's accountable for RDM and DM
		Transparency of policies

Balance metadata requirements in a reasonable amount of time that other people will read it	Data discovery and reuse	Paying people to know when to share data, when is for patients etc and paying for patients' data copyrights
Keeping data annotated		People power - pay for people time to analyse and improve data quality for future discoverability and reuse
Machine vs Human discoverability and reuse		Having data stewards
Software and hardware obsolescence		
Sharing data with ID's that are universally recognised; sharing data with the latest updated correctly annotated		